

CRITICALITY OF IMPACT DAMAGE IN COMPOSITE SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Composite materials structures have to tolerate barely visible, low velocity, impact damage, which inevitably occurs during the service life of the structure. Visible damage has to be detected and repaired. In the present work an analytical and experimental study was performed to demonstrate the ability of specific sandwich structures to tolerate barely visible impact damage. The analytical approach is based on the calculation of the residual compression strength of the damaged laminate. The experimental phase consists of two stages. First, the barely visible damage has been defined and the damage characterized. Next, beam specimens, containing impact damage as defined in the first stage, have been tested in 4 point bending. A good correlation between the experimentally measured and analytically predicted strength reductions has been obtained.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials aircraft structures have to conform to damage tolerance requirements. Damage occurring in the structure during fabrication, usage or maintenance, should be either detected repaired or tolerated for the entire aircraft life without failure. McCarty and Harton [1], have recently summarised the philosophy and methodology of damage tolerance in composite materials. They have emphasized that impact damage is the most critical damage which has to be tolerated during normal service, causing a bigger strength reduction than holes, cracks, delaminations or porosity regions of the same size. Composite structures are substantiated in compliance with ref. [2,3,4,5,6] for civil aircraft and [7,8] for military aircraft. The requirements considering impact damage are similar for both civil and military categories, namely: non-visible impact damage should be tolerated by the structure, visible damage should be repaired.

The common substantiation procedure is experimental. The energy causing Barely Visible Damage (BVD) is measured, than representative specimens or structural elements are subjected to this impact energy and tested mechanically to demonstrate ultimate load bearing capability and

life durability. In order to reduce the amount of testing and base the substantiation on analysis, the impact damage has to be characterized and models have to be developed to relate between the damage and the damaged structure strength. The characterization of the impact damage and its influence on compression strength of laminated composites has been extensively investigated. Rhodes [9,10] compared damage resulting from ballistic and drop tests and characterized this damage showing the importance of delaminations. Farelley [11], reported strength reduction due to penetration of ballistic and low velocity impact. Guynn and O'Brien [12] investigated experimentally the influence of lay-up and thickness on the damage pattern caused by the impact and the reduction in compressive strength due to this damage. Lee [13] studied the influence of matrix toughness on compression strength after impact. Further development of analytical methods which link the impact damage to the strength after impact is strongly needed.

In the present work an analytical and experimental study was performed to demonstrate the ability of sandwich structures to tolerate barely visible impact damage. The analysis is based on a simplistic model, adequate for sandwich structures with thin composite skins, developed in a previous work [14].

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental phase consists of two stages. First the BVD has been defined and the damage characterized. Next, beam specimens, containing impact damage as defined in the first stage, have been tested in bending. The strength reduction was compared to the one predicted by the analytical model.

Damage Characterization Experiments

Sandwich beams build of AS4/3502 graphite/epoxy skins of 5, 7 and 11 layers and aluminium H/C were impacted by a standard blunt 1.0 in diameter, 3 lbs weight, hemispherical impactor (Fig. 1). The impact energy was determined by the height from which the impactor was dropped. Increasing energies have been applied until visible damage was obtained and the visibility threshold has been established. Fig. 2 shows the impacted beam.

The energy level at which the 3 different laminates have reached BVD is given in Table 1. After impacting, the specimens were inspected non-destructively by ultrasonic through transmission. The circles on the specimen in Fig. 2 represent the size of the maximal delamination at each impact. The findings of the NDT are represented schematically in Table 2. It can be seen that the major delamination is accompanied by small delaminations at different levels. The diameter of the major delamination, as a function of the impact energy is given in Fig. 3. The size of the internal damage is constant over a large range of energies, and is not changed at the visible threshold. The visible threshold is the energy level at which fiber damage occurs in addition to internal delamination. The size of the internal delamination is controlled by the impactor shape, this implies that in service, when tools of different geometries may fall on composite structures, internal damages of different dimensions may be obtained. The independence of the internal damage on the BVD, shows that the impact energy is not an appropriate measure of the damage produced by impact.

Mechanical Experiments

Beam specimens with the same laminates as previously described, were impacted at the BVD energies given in Table 1 and tested to failure in 4 points bending, with the impacted skin in compression (Fig. 4). In order to avoid tensile failure, the tension skins were designed stronger than the compression skins. Specimens were tested at room temperature, as manufactured (R.T.D.) and at 100 deg. C., after being preconditioned to 1.1% moisture in the skins (H.W.). The moisture conditioning was performed after impacting, so that the worst absorption conditions were provided. Measured residual strengths of impacted specimens are given in Table 3. In addition, Table 3 contains results of strength reduction due to artificial delaminations, located at the same position as the impact damage, obtained in Ref. [14].

TABLE 1
BVD Energies for Different Sandwich Specimens

SPECIMEN TYPE	UPPER-LAYER LAMINATE	H/C	BVD ENERGY [KN·MM]
I	[<u>+</u> 45,0, <u>+</u> 45]	AL- $\frac{1}{8}$ " - 5056-0.0020-8.1pcf	13.6
II	[<u>+</u> 45,0,90,0 <u>+</u> 45]	AL- $\frac{1}{8}$ " - 5056-0.0020-8.1pcf	17.0
III	[<u>+</u> 45,0 ₃ ,90,0 ₃ <u>+</u> 45]	AL- $\frac{1}{8}$ " - 5052-0.006-22.1pcf	27.2

Figure 1: Impact Set-Up

TABLE 2
Damage Characterization for Different Specimens

SPECIMEN TYPE	DAMAGE GEOMETRY	
	UPPER VIEW	SIDE VIEW
I		
II		
III		

Figure 2. BVD on Composite Sandwich

Figure 3: Damage Diameter as a Function of Impact Energy

Figure 4: Mechanical Test Set-Up

ANALYSIS

Failure Mechanism

Figures 5, 6 and 7 show failed specimens without initial damage, containing impact damage and containing an artificial delamination. The failure mode of undamaged specimens is compression failure of the laminate. The presence of an artificial delamination causes buckling of the laminate above the delamination and then the laminate below the delamination fails in compression. Specimens containing impact damage fail in a most complex mode. Since the BVD considered, includes some fiber failure, the laminate above the delamination is ineffective from the first stages of loading. Some buckling of the skin above the delamination around the damaged fibers occurs and then the laminate fails when the sublaminates below the delamination fails in compression.

Failure Model

A failure model for a sandwich beam containing a delamination was developed in [14] and found to predict conservatively experimental results. This failure analysis is based on considering separately the laminate above the delamination and the laminate below the delamination. The load is divided between the two sublaminates according to classical lamination theory. The upper laminate is checked against buckling and net compression failure; the lower sublaminates against compression failure alone, since buckling is prevented by the adhesion of the skin to the H/C core. When one of the sublaminates fails, the load is transferred to the other sublaminates, until it also fails. Buckling analysis is performed by a bifurcation method, based on the principle of minimum potential energy simplified with the use of Ritz method [15]. The laminate is assumed to be statistically homogeneous and anisotropic with effective elastic moduli and bending stiffnesses. Compression failure of the laminate is calculated according to classical lamination theory and first ply maximum stress failure criterion [16]. The analytical methods, being well known and widely used are not described here. The analysis was performed by means of computer programs based on references [15] and [16]. When the delamination is caused by impact, it usually occurs on the weakest planes, from the point of view of interlaminar shear and is accompanied by fiber breakage in the upper layers and additional small delaminations at different levels. These special damage patterns cause the laminate above the delamination to become ineffective at early stages of the mechanical loading. The load is thus transferred to the intact laminate below the damage; in other words the strength of the structure is controlled by the compression strength of the laminate not affected by the impact. Thus, the analysis consists of assessing the compressive strength of the laminate below the damage.

Table 3 presents the correlation between the strength predicted analytically to the strength measured experimentally.

Figure 5: Failed Specimen; Laminate with No Initial Damage

Figure 6: Failed Specimen; Laminate with Artificial Delamination

Figure 7: Failed Specimen, with Impact Damage

TABLE 3
Failure Load for 4 Point Bending Sandwich
Specimens; Test and Analysis Results

SPECIMEN TYPE	TEST COND.	INSTRON FAILURE LOAD [KG]					
		UNDAMAGED		ART. DEL		IMPACT	
		EXP.(1)	ANAL.	EXP.(1)	ANAL.	EXP.(1)	ANAL.
I	R.T.D.	480	394			315	105
	H.W.					250	99
II	R.T.D.	1637	1134	647	396	500	284
	H.W.					415	275
III	R.T.D.	3180	2695	1224	723	1178	974
	H.W.					1040	984

(1) Average Result of 3-4 tests, $3 < c.v. < 20$.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The response of sandwich composite specimens to low velocity impact damage was considered as part of a structural substantiation program. The nature of the produced damage was inspected and related to the strength reduction it caused. A simple analytic model was built to assess the strength reduction due to induced damage and found to conform with measured strength reductions.

Damage characterization experiments have shown that the BVD energy is not a quantity that defines the damage or the residual strength of the damaged structure. The damage pattern is strongly dependent on the geometry of the impactor. The only characteristic property which defines the strength reduction is the actual damage present in the structure.

Impact damage caused by low velocity collisions of standard impactors, on composite sandwich structures consists of delaminations through the thickness of the skin, accompanied by fiber breakage in the upper layers. This damage pattern causes a failure mechanism where the damaged part of the laminate becomes ineffective and the strength of the sandwich is controlled by the compressive strength of the undamaged laminate, below the delamination. The damage produced by impact is more critical to the structure than artificial delaminations, due to the presence of secondary delaminations and broken fibers. Environmental effects influence strength reduction due to impact at the extent they affect the compression strength of the intact laminate.

The analytical model developed and checked in the present work has the advantage of being simplistic. It is based on classical lamination theory and can be easily performed on every structure, when the local loads and the damage pattern are known.

The obtained strength is consistently conservative when compared with experimental data (Table 3), since existing load bearing capability of the damaged laminate and load transfer to adjacent layers after first ply failure are neglected. The use of this model can reduce the amount of testing required for substantiation and provide a tool to assess the criticality of in service damage, if detected and characterized.

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